

Urban Cycling: Intelligent Bicycle Sensors for Road Safety and Sustainability

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Abstract

Urban transportation is rapidly evolving with a growing emphasis on sustainability and smart city development. Cycling, a cornerstone of sustainable urban mobility, requires reliable data for effective integration into city planning. However, there remains a critical gap in the comprehensive collection and analysis of cycling-specific environmental and safety data. Addressing this gap, this work introduces an innovative bicycle sensor system that utilises embedded artificial intelligence (AI) to process data on-device. By reducing data overhead and enhancing privacy, this system offers a novel approach to improving cycling safety and contributing to smarter urban transportation planning. Our sensor system integrates road surface classification and overtaking detection, employing edge computing to minimise energy consumption and data transmission, while still delivering actionable insights for city planners and cyclists alike. A workshop conducted with citizens, followed by a survey, evaluated user experiences, revealing valuable insights into usability, connectivity, and areas for improvement, including connection stability and data continuity. Although our AI models showed promising results, they were constrained by limited training data and sampling rates, highlighting areas for future refinement. This work shows the potential of integrating EmbeddedAI within cycling infrastructure planning to enhance road safety, and such mobile sensor systems to engage communities in urban mobility efforts.

1. Introduction

Urban transportation is transforming with a focus on sustainability and smart city initiatives. Cycling, a key element of sustainable urban mobility, needs robust infrastructure and reliable data for growth and integration into city planning. Despite advancements in sensor technology and (geo)data analytics, there is a gap in comprehensive collection and use of cycling-specific environmental, safety, and pathway data.

One major deterrent for citizens using bicycles are the perceived dangers in traffic (Ipsos, 2022). These perceived dangers can discourage people from choosing bicycles as a mode of transportation, undermining efforts to promote cycling as a safe, sustainable, and healthy alternative (Jacobsen et al., 2009). Identifying unsafe sections is therefore crucial to improving cycling infrastructure. Countermeasures can change negative perceptions and promote cycling as a safe and sustainable mode of transport. Traditionally, only actual accidents are included in official data, informing city planning decision makers. However, analysing high-risk occurrences like near-miss incidents, which greatly impact the perceived danger, can provide a more accurate understanding of cycling safety.

In particular, dangerously close overtaking manoeuvres by motorists pose a significant risk, not only increasing the likelihood of accidents but also amplifying the perceived dangers associated with cycling. Several countries, including Brazil and Germany, have enacted laws requiring motorists to maintain a minimum distance when overtaking cyclists; however, actual compliance with these laws is often lacking (Casey et al., 2024).

There already exist a number of projects using different technologies to gather and provide data on bicycle safety. For

example CycleAI¹ leverages AI to evaluate the safety of roads based on static images, offering safer route suggestions but lacking real-time environmental and temporal considerations. Specifically for detecting dangerously close takeover manoeuvres, ultrasonic sensors are often employed, for example by the OpenBikeSensor² project. With their developed hardware, the cyclist can manually trigger a button on their bike to start measuring distance with an ultrasonic sensor mounted on the bike. On the downside, manual activation can lead to missed or inaccurate data in high-stress situations. Fully automatic systems like "Sicher überholt!" (Blees, 2021) and "Radmesser" (Lehmann et al., 2018) combine smartphone cameras with ultrasonic sensors for more reliable data collection, though they raise concerns about privacy and higher data overhead and energy usage.

Another important factor in determining the cyclability of an area is the type of road surfaces cyclists encounter. Road surface conditions significantly affect the comfort and safety of cycling. Recent studies have used accelerometers and various processing methods to analyse road surfaces and conditions. A common approach is to classify bumpiness, roughness or individual road damages based on accelerometer data using either classical algorithms (Zange et al., 2018) or machine learning techniques (Hoffmann et al., 2013; Setiawan et al., 2020; Kim and Kim, 2024). Heidt and Dorer (2021) and Wang et al. (2021) instead classified several road surface types (such as asphalt or gravel). While Wang et al. (2021) reported the highest classification accuracy using gradient-boosted decision trees, Heidt and Dorer (2021) found that deep and shallow neural networks gave the most accurate classifications. The insights gained by these automatic evaluation efforts are valuable for city

¹ <https://cycleai.net/> (last visited 28.08.2024)

² <https://www.openbikesensor.org/> (last visited 28.06.2024)

planners to prioritise maintenance and upgrades to cycling infrastructure.

Our research effort is unique in the sense that it integrates both road safety and environmental sensing aspects. Thereby, it combines individual components such as road surface classification and takeover detection into an innovative bicycle sensor system that leverages embedded artificial intelligence (AI) to process sensor data on the device. This approach has the potential to reduce data overhead and address privacy concerns while simultaneously providing actionable insights. By carrying out the main processing of the data on the device, in accordance with the concept of edge computing, we reduce the data load that has to be transmitted, which in turn reduces the overall energy consumption of the system (Muhosa et al., 2023). Unlike traditional microcontroller-based sensing systems, which can be complex to assemble and often require technical skills and specialised equipment, our solution aims to keep the hardware setup as simple as possible to allow broad accessibility.

Ultimately, our work has the potential to make significant contributions to traffic and transport planning by providing valuable insights into traffic patterns and road safety concerns using extensive spatial datasets gathered by citizens.

2. System Design

At the core of our system is an ESP32-S2 based microcontroller unit (MCU) of the senseBox (Wirwahn et al., 2015) family. The senseBox is a versatile, open hardware electronics kit designed specifically for citizen science projects and educational initiatives, with an emphasis on environmental monitoring and data collection (Witte et al., 2023).

The following environmental sensors are used:

1. Temperature & Relative Humidity (HDC1080)
2. Particulate Matter (SPS30)
3. Acceleration (MPU6050)
4. Time-of-Flight (ToF) ranging (VL53L8CX)

Moreover, battery management, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), and OLED-Display modules are included for connectivity and user feedback. All parts fit into a custom designed, 3D printed enclosure which is attached to the seat post of a bicycle (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Photo of our sensor device showing left side with ToF distance sensor

Figure 2. A conceptual model of the system including sensors, microcontroller, app, and database.

The device is communicating with a hybrid, open-source Capacitor- and React-based smartphone app³ using BLE, which receives sensor data and combines it with geolocation data (Figure 2). Datasets are recorded and saved on the smartphone, but can also be uploaded to openSenseMap (Pfeil et al., 2015) as open data during the ride.

The app provides real-time data display in numerical and graphical formats (as shown in Figure 3), allowing cyclists to monitor key information while they ride. It also offers functionalities for starting and stopping data recording, accessing an interactive map, and keeping control over their digital sovereignty by defining privacy zones where data collection is paused. After completing their rides, cyclists can review their data in detail through the app’s “Tracks” section, which provides comprehensive graphs and maps of the collected information.

In addition, if cyclists agree to share their data through the app settings, it is uploaded to the open data platform openSenseMap. On this platform, cyclists and other users can download the data, explore it with interactive maps, and filter the data based on their specific needs. This collaborative approach supports the community’s efforts to enhance cycling safety and sustainability in urban environments.

2.1 Machine Learning on the Bike

We are introducing two approaches to utilise machine learning capabilities using LiteRT⁴ (formerly known as TensorFlow Lite) and Edge Impulse⁵ on the sensor device: overtaking detection and road surface classification. By processing the data directly on the device instead of sending it to larger servers, bandwidth and energy consumption is kept minimal.

³ <https://github.com/reedu-reengineering-education/sensebox-bike-app> (last visited 27.06.2024)

⁴ <https://ai.google.dev/edge/litert> (last visited 12.09.2024)

⁵ <https://edgeimpulse.com/> (last visited 29.07.2024)

Figure 3: Screenshot of senseBox:bike app visualising live location and environmental data

2.1.1 Detecting dangerously close takeover manoeuvres

We propose a method for automatically detecting and recording dangerously close overtaking manoeuvres by processing low-resolution depth images captured by a VL53L8CX ToF imager. This processing is performed using shallow neural networks directly on the microcontroller unit (MCU). An initial standalone version of this workflow has previously already been detailed by Scharf et al. (2024), where a small Long short-term memory (LSTM) based neural network was utilised for data processing. The network is set up and trained in TensorFlow on a dedicated desktop computer. To run the trained model on the microcontroller unit it has to first be converted to LiteRT and then to LiteRT for Microcontrollers.

However, it was observed that LSTM-based models suffer a significant loss of detection accuracy when converted from TensorFlow to LiteRT. This issue is not faced by models based on convolutional layers, which is why for this work a shallow Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was designed instead.

Given that only a single processing core is available on the microcontroller for recording and processing of all sensor data, it is essential to keep the inference time of the takeover detection model as low as possible. The inference time directly affects the frequency at which new sensor data can be recorded. In combination with the other sensor processing and transmitting tasks, a recording frequency of 10 Hz can be achieved, which already is incredibly low for the takeover detection and even more problematic for the road surface classification. At lower frequencies it becomes almost impossible to infer the direction of the passing vehicle, especially if the passing vehicle is moving much faster than the user.

Figure 4. Prediction workflow employed for road surface classification

With these constraints in mind the CNN structure in Figure 4 is ultimately chosen. As a LiteRT model, it achieves a prediction accuracy of about 96% (determined by tenfold cross-validation) on the ground truth data. When deployed on an ESP32-S2 MCU the model achieves an inference time of 47 ms and requires a little more than 6 KB of memory space to store and less than 12 KB of RAM for inference. The code and data used for training, and the model itself have been published on GitHub⁶.

On the microcontroller, each newly recorded depth frame is added to a ring buffer, with the most recent 20 frames being fed to the model for prediction.

2.1.2 Road Surface Classification

To automatically classify road surfaces, we trained a neural network on acceleration and gyroscopic data collected by an MPU6050 acceleration sensor. Even if the road surface type has already been classified in the past, automatic live classification is still valuable to enhance such existing maps. This approach reflects the current condition of the road the cyclist is using, providing a finer level of detail compared to potentially more generalised previous classifications. In that manner it can reveal deviations between the intended and actual road surfaces. For example, a section of asphalt road might be so riddled with potholes and bumps that it behaves more like cobblestone (sett) than smooth asphalt when ridden over.

We focused on classifying four surface types commonly found in OpenStreetMap⁷: asphalt, compacted, paving, and sett. Additionally, we included a "standing" class to filter out instances where the cyclist is stationary, ensuring that only relevant data is analysed.

Our proposed classification workflow operates as follows: Acceleration and Gyroscope Data is recorded at 10 Hz over a 3-second window. The 10 Hz recording frequency is the maximum achievable given the simultaneous takeover detection. The window length of 3 seconds was chosen as a

⁶ <https://github.com/TinyAIoT/tof-takeover-detection> (last visited 05.09.24)

⁷ <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:surface> (last visited 10.09.2024)

compromise between having sufficient data points for accurate classification and maintaining a reasonable frequency of classifications. From the raw data collected, several spectral features are computed, including spectral power across different frequencies, kurtosis, skewness, and root mean square (RMS). These spectral features are then fed into a shallow dense neural network for classification.

Figure 5. Prediction workflow employed for road surface classification

To implement this workflow, we utilised Edge Impulse, a platform that allows for the entire process to be exported as an Arduino library based on LiteRT (TensorFlow Lite), which can be directly deployed on the microcontroller. Edge Impulse was chosen primarily due to its efficient implementation of spectral feature calculation and its easy to use end-to-end workflow of training and deploying a neural network. Our trained model, the training workflow and the utilised training data can be viewed in EdgImpulse⁸.

For training the neural network, ground truth data was recorded with the hardware mounted on two separate bicycles and driven around Münster, Germany at varying speeds by two different cyclists. This data was then manually labelled. To ensure the training data represented "clean" examples of each road surface type, we used a k-means algorithm on each individual recording to filter out any anomalies (such as bumps and potholes). Segments where the cyclist was starting or stopping were also excluded to maintain a clear distinction between the "standing" and "non-standing" classes. After cleaning and pruning a total 27 minutes and 39 seconds of data remained for training, validation and testing.

The resulting confusion matrix of the model trained on this ground truth data is given in Table 1. While sett and "standing" surfaces are predicted very accurately with 100%, asphalt, compacted and paving surfaces are harder to differentiate using the training data.

⁸ <https://studio.edgeimpulse.com/public/440960/live> (last visited 02.09.2024)

Act\Pred	Asphalt	Compacted	Paving	Sett	Standing
Asphalt	64.9	14.0	15.8	0.0	3.5
Compacted	9.1	72.7	9.1	0.0	0.0
Paving	12.8	10.3	71.8	2.6	2.6
Sett	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0
Standing	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0

Table 1. Confusion Matrix of the trained model on the test set of the collected ground truth data with a confidence threshold of 0.4. The average accuracy over all classes is 79.21%

3. Workshops

Engaging citizens in data collection, problem identification, and the construction of sensor stations empowers them and fosters the generation of new ideas (Serrano Sanz et al., 2014). We conducted a workshop in São Paulo, Brazil, where 13 participants checked the hardware setup and mounted their mobile sensor device on bicycles (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Participants assembling the box and checking the mounting system before the trial. Photo by Mario Pesch (2024)

After assembling the equipment, participants connected the device to the application on their phones and conducted a 30-minute trial, collecting environmental and bicycle-specific data as they cycled around the Largo da Batata area in western São Paulo, Brazil. This initial trial was followed by a brief open-question session, after which the participants were allowed to keep the equipment for two days. At the end of this period, a two-hour group interview was conducted to gather detailed feedback, organised by specific topics (Figure 7).

In autumn of 2024 more follow-up workshops will be held in Münster, Germany which will allow the comparison of the contrasting bicycle infrastructures in these cities, as well as the general urban environment differences, and will provide valuable data and insights into participants' perceptions.

This collaborative effort enhances participants' understanding of scientific methods and urban mobility challenges while ensuring that the collected data reflects cyclists' authentic experiences. By involving citizens as active contributors, we aim to bridge the gap between scientific research and

community needs, fostering a more inclusive and participatory approach to urban mobility solutions.

Figure 7: Feedback round after the two days of testing the system. Photo by Camila Cavalheiro (2024)

After the workshops we conduct user studies with the workshop participants on the following topics:

1. Usability: participants provide feedback on assembling, mounting and connecting the bicycle sensor device.
2. Data Literacy: Participants evaluate their understanding about the data displayed on the app.
3. Trust in Data: Participants review the data of their recorded dangerous takeovers and road surface types and compare its accuracy with their own perceptions.

The individual survey questions are given in Appendix 8.1.

4. Survey Results

After the workshop, a voluntary survey was offered to participants, with 10 of them completing it. Additionally, a two-hour feedback session was held during the second day of the workshop, allowing participants to freely share suggestions and describe any technical difficulties they encountered. The survey, combined with the feedback session results, provides a comprehensive overview of participants' experiences, highlighting areas of success and identifying potential improvements for the project.

The volunteer group was evenly split by gender, with 50% identifying as male and 50% as female, and 60% aged between 31–40 years. Additionally, 50% of participants cycle daily, with 70% of them covering distances between 10 to 100 km per day. Regarding technology usage, 90% reported having little to no experience with sensors.

In terms of hardware and software usability, most volunteers found the system easy to set up, register on the app, and connect to the open data platform. They found the sensor box, mounted behind the seat, comfortable and unobtrusive to carry, but suggested improvements to the mounting system for better stability on bumpy roads. Participants recommended also installing a distance sensor to the right side to account for the variability in the layout of the city's

bike lanes. While many participants found it easy to connect the app to the sensor system, most experienced frequent disconnections, which disrupted data collection.

Regarding data visualisation in the app, many participants found the information easy to understand but offered suggestions for improving interaction with the data. For example, some volunteers expressed a desire to navigate the map and follow the timeline in the graphs.

Participants also suggested notifications to remind them to start data collection, along with automatically stopping data collection when the location remains stationary for a few minutes. Additionally, they noted issues with the application's slow performance when checking collected data, which sometimes required them to restart the app to access the information.

Finally, the accuracy perception of the data was affected by connectivity issues, making it difficult for volunteers to assess the data, as many routes were interrupted, and some data could not be stored or viewed after completion. This is also reflected in a prevalent "neutral" rating of perceived prediction accuracy (see Figure 8).

5. Limitations

The results indicate challenges in the stability of the connection between device and smartphone, which affected the ability to collect data of longer bicycle rides. While data was successfully acquired, it was often limited to shorter segments of just a few minutes. These issues overshadow the data collection, resulting in incomplete and inconsistent datasets that hinder comprehensive analysis and limit the reliability of conclusions drawn about bicycle safety.

Our AI models also face some specific limitations, including constrained training data and a low sampling rate. The training data was collected using only two bicycles and only in Münster, Germany, which may not provide sufficient variety to accurately detect different road surfaces across a wider range of bicycles and riding conditions. Additionally, Our sampling rate of 10 Hz is low in comparison to similar solutions (Heidt & Dorer, 2021; Wang et al., 2021). In fact when we train the model on the same ground truth data but at 333 Hz we see an increase of the average classification accuracy of about 6 percent compared to a recording frequency of 10 Hz.

6. Future Work

By utilising a multi-core MCU in the future, higher sample rates of the sensors could be achieved by distributing the computational load across different cores.

The AI model to detect overtaking manoeuvres currently only returns its probability of a detected manoeuvre. Extending the output classes of the model and including overtaking vehicles (bike, car, truck, ...), overtaking speed, or detecting static objects can increase data diversity and thus allow for more detailed insights into bicycle safety. Additionally, incorporating a second distance sensor with an opposite orientation would offer a more comprehensive view of the cyclist's environment, capturing the available space for manoeuvring and evading obstacles.

Figure 8: How did participants perceive the accuracy of the data

Regarding connectivity issues, a new app based on a different underlying framework (Flutter) is currently under development. Preliminary tests indicate improved connection stability and overall enhanced app performance.

Next steps in the project include the development of an open source bicycle related data analysis platform as a recommender system for bicycle infrastructure measures in cities. Providing interactive visualisations allows city planners and decision makers, but also cyclists to explore potentially hazardous sections, within or outside of cities.

7. Conclusion

This research highlights the critical role of integrating road safety and environmental data into cycling infrastructure planning. By developing a novel sensor system that combines road surface classification and overtaking detection through embedded AI, we address significant gaps in existing cycling data collection methods. Our approach, leveraging edge computing to process data on the device, minimises energy consumption, data overhead, and privacy concerns, while still delivering actionable insights for city planners and cyclists alike.

This comprehensive evaluation aims to provide a thorough understanding of both the user experience and the technical performance of the system. Workshops conducted with citizen participants demonstrated the system's potential to engage communities in cycling safety efforts, though technical challenges such as connection stability and data continuity need further refinement. Moreover, our AI models showed promising results but are constrained by limited training data and low sampling rates. Future work will focus on improving hardware, expanding data collection capabilities, and enhancing the app's functionality to provide a more seamless user experience.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Survey Design

- 1) Questions about the User (all have the option to not answer)
 - a) Age or age-span
 - b) Gender
 - c) Current Occupation
 - d) Highest completed level of education
 - i) Incomplete Elementary School
 - ii) Completed Elementary School
 - iii) Incomplete High School
 - iv) Completed High School
 - v) Incomplete Technical Education
 - vi) Completed Technical Education
 - vii) Incomplete Higher Education
 - viii) Completed Higher Education
 - ix) Incomplete Postgraduate/Master's Degree
 - x) Completed Postgraduate/Master's Degree
 - xi) Incomplete Doctorate
 - xii) Completed Doctorate
 - e) Experience with sensors?
 - i) No experience

- ii) Basic experience (occasional use of sensors)
- iii) Intermediate experience (regular use of sensors in personal projects or similar)
- iv) Advanced experience (development or integration of sensors in projects)
- v) Expert (research, development, or teaching about sensors)
- vi) Prefer not to answer
- f) How often do you cycle in the city ?
 - i) Daily
 - ii) A few times a week
 - iii) Once a week
 - iv) A few times a month
 - v) Rarely
- g) What's the KM average per week ?
 - i) Less than 10 km
 - ii) Between 10 km and 20 km
 - iii) Between 20 km and 50 km
 - iv) Between 50 km and 100 km
 - v) Between 100 km and 200 km
 - vi) More than 200 km

2) Usability

- a) How easy was it to set up (openSenseMap user registration and box) (Likert scale: Easy to Difficult)
- b) How comfortable were you with carrying or attaching the device in the bike? (Likert scale: Very Comfortable to Uncomfortable)
- c) How difficult was it to connect the application to senseBox:Bike? (Likert scale: Easy to Difficult)
- d) How clear were the instructions for mounting the senseBox:Bike to the bike and connecting the app? (Likert scale: Easy to Difficult)
- e) How stable was the connection ? (Likert scale: Unstable (no connection) to Very stable (100% connected))
 - i) If you answer unstable, could you give us some examples of disconnection ?

3) Data Visualization

- a) How easy was it to understand the technology concepts ? (Likert scale: Easy to Difficult)
- b) How easy was it to understand the data visualisations presented during the app (section tracks) ? (Likert scale: Easy to Difficult)
- c) How useful did you find the real-time data visualisation on your smartphone ? (Likert scale: useless to very useful)
- d) What additional features would you like to see on the app to data understanding ?

4) Trust in Data

- a) How accurate did you find the (Likert scale: Very inaccurate to very accurate) ?
 - i) Overtaking distance
 - ii) Road Surface Classification
 - iii) Fine Dust measurements
 - iv) Temperature measurements
 - v) Geolocation

- a) Did you encounter any instances where the device misclassified data or showed incorrect data ? (e.g., road surface type, environmental conditions, or overtaking manoeuvres)?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
 - c) Prefer not to say
- b) If yes, please provide a brief description of the misclassification(s) you observed:
- c) How frequently did these misclassifications occur?
 - a) Never
 - b) Rarely
 - c) Sometimes
 - d) Often
 - e) Very Frequently
- d) What additional information or data points would you like to collect with the device or app?